

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D5.1 – Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment I

WP5 AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalised
Recommendations

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Author name(s)	Thanos Kalligeris (ATC), Giorgos Giotis (ATC), Maritini Kalogerini (ATC), Spyros Papafragkos (ATC), Anastasios Pantazidis (iSPRINT), Aristodemos Pnevmatikakis (iSPRINT), Krasimir Filipov (KOD)
Reviewer name(s)	Gabriel Michail (SIE), Tanja Tomson (KI)

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Executive summary

This report summarizes the actions performed under Task 5.1 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment I” and more specifically provides details of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML) algorithms and implementation techniques that will be used to perform early identification as well as predictions of Pancreatic Cancer (PC) risks in individuals. The deliverable brings together several AI/ML techniques that are expected to be able to identify hidden patterns and trends in given data. When the data become available in the next phase of the project, these techniques will be used for performing assessment of identified risks and subsequently for making predictions. Since this is the first version of a series of deliverables, the follow-up report (i.e. D5.2) will specify the techniques to be used and linked with the datasets collected from the project pilots.

1 Introduction

Patients with Pancreatic Cancer (PC) are diagnosed at later stages of the disease when curative therapy is hardly achievable which in turn results in low survival rates and as such PC is an important public health burden (P., O., N., + 20), (M., R., Q., 08), (C., F., D., + 15). In most cases, it takes years before a diagnosis is realized since most of the patients display non-specific symptoms during this time (O., C., G., 17). Continuous evolution related to cancer research has been achieved (W., R., H., + 11), in the last few years, however, progress towards an early cancer diagnosis has been slow (E., R., B., + 13), (S., M., 10). The fact that population-based screening for pancreatic cancer is not feasible when considering low probability of PC (ranges between 0.0003 and 0.003 among ages of 40–59 and 80–99 respectively) (P., B., S., + 17), (C., R., S., 2019), results in a prohibitively expensive scheme (P., O., N., + 20), (S., K., C., + 19). Targeted screening, on the other hand, is a possibility. Diagnostic biomarkers (D., M., C., + 19), (S., D., J., + 14) have been identified from numerous studies, and the most promising results have been obtained using protein markers (B., Z., C., + 20), (R., M., J., + 15) either alone or in combination with the clinically established biomarker, CA 19–9 (C., L., W., + 18). These studies mostly identify high-risk groups containing small numbers of people, for example, those with at least two affected first-degree relatives or individuals with known underlying gene abnormalities (L., W., C., + 14).

With the emergence of new technologies in the field of medicine, large amounts of cancer-related data have been collected and are available to the medical research community. AI/ML methods have become an increasingly popular tool for medical researchers. These methods can identify patterns and relationships among several features collected from complex datasets, while they are able to effectively predict future outcomes of a specific cancer type.

This research work presents the AI/ML approaches that can be later employed for the objectives of the project to be realized and specifically for early risk identification and predictions. Keeping in mind that task T5.1 will further extend the models considered in T4.1 but taking also into account the real time/prospective data, we here present those techniques that have been used in other studies with similar objectives in order to prepare for the next phase of the project, when the initial prospective data and the prospective data after a while will be available.

1.1 Scope of the document

The scope of this document is to summarize the work done under T5.1 - “Techniques for Early Risk Identification, Predictions and Assessment”, during the first 10 months of the Task’s duration. The aim of D5.1 is to gather details of the AI algorithms and implementation techniques that will be used during the project’s lifetime, in order to enable early identification of Pancreatic Cancer. The ultimate goal is to reveal hidden patterns and trends in real-time/prospective data, in order to make predictions and also perform assessment of identified risks. More specifically, the AI algorithms and the implementation techniques that will be realized during the iHelp project, will be described in a series of deliverables starting from D5.1 - “Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment” and will be followed by two updates II and III, on M22 and M32, respectively. Due to the lack of available datasets during the first period of the project, the first document (out of three) aims to set the basis, in a more theoretical level, for the two upcoming deliverables.

1.2 Structure of the document

A brief description of every section of this deliverable follows.

- Section 1 consists of the documents' introduction, the connection with other WPs as well as the background work that is related to T5.1.
- Section 2 describes the preparation of the secondary data.
- Section 3 presents the supervised learning methods and algorithms that can be exploited in the context of T5.1.
- Section 4 introduces the unsupervised learning methods in healthcare that could be used in the context of iHelp.
- Section 5 presents a brief overview of the survival estimation analysis and some potential algorithms to approach it.
- Section 6 presents the workflow for the learning of predictive and generative models on synthetic data through a simulator.
- Section 7 checks the applicability of the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI.
- Section 9 concludes this document.

1.3 Relevance with other Work Packages

Task T5.1 concerns the methods and the AI techniques that will be developed during the lifetime of the project, for the realization of the risk prediction models, also taking into account the secondary data. It is considered a significant task for the project outcomes, however it is mainly related to WPs 3 and 4. WP3 is responsible for the mapping activities into Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resource (FHIR) and the final storage in the Holistic Health Records (HHR) platform, WP4 and more specifically T4.1 - "Personalized Health Modelling and Predictions" is directly connected to T5.1, since in T4.1 the AI models are first introduced and analyzed taking into account the retrospective data. Then in T5.1 we further analyze the AI models and techniques and taking into consideration also the real-time/prospective data we improve the predictions and generally the outcomes of this task.

1.4 Background

Pancreatic cancer (PC) constitutes a substantial public health problem. Patients suffering from PC have very low probabilities of living more than a few years due to the difficulty of identifying this specific type of cancer early enough when the tumour is localised to the site of origin and is treatable. Furthermore, it is widely accepted that PC is not a good candidate for mass population-based screening due to its low incidence in the general population. As small as 10% of the patients diagnosed with pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) have either a strong family history of PC, hereditary pancreatitis or a particular genetic syndrome (P., O., N., + 20). The remaining 90% of PDAC patients are non-inherited cases who overwhelmingly display no alarm symptoms until the tumour is well-advanced. Recent studies have been conducted, mainly in identifying biomarkers for PC in the blood and urine, but these cannot be used for population-based screening as this would be prohibitively expensive and potentially harmful. Furthermore, other works in the literature have highlighted putative features associated with PC diagnosis such as jaundice, abdominal pain, back pain, gastric problems, weight loss, malaise and new-onset diabetes (S., P., N., + 12), (H., C., B., + 04).

2 Pre-processing of secondary data

As with any type of real world data in the case of health related data and streaming data it is probable that a variety of factors (e.g. design, device malfunction, patient's characteristics or dropping out) will lead to missing data values. Most if not all state-of-the-art models that take temporal relationships into consideration operate on regularly structured time data. Therefore, there is a need to substitute these missing values and the process of filling these with suitable values is called *imputation* and specifically for time series *interpolation*. It should be noted that interpolation does not increase performance but instead allows the model to operate in situations where a reasonable percentage of missingness in data exists (no more than 40%). In contrast to *extrapolation*, interpolation only predicts missing values from data and not future values. This means that this chapter does not address time series prediction.

Figure 1: Time series with missing values

Padding Interpolation

The simplest solution to the problem is to assume that the missing value is the same as the last seen value. This way if a range of values are missing they are all filled with the last observed value in the time series. This technique is referred to as *padding interpolation* and is useful in cases where we don't want to alter the data at all but still want to perform analysis on them. Even though it is obviously not an ideal option it is a quick workaround to the missing value problem and can be used as a simple solution when we just want to test the next stages of an ML pipeline.

Linear Interpolation

The simplest form of estimating the values of a time series is to suppose that they derive from the available values in a linear manner. In this case to estimate a missing value, the two closest non missing values are used to fit a line and the missing value of the point is derived by supposing that it is on the same line. Usually the values that are missing are continuous time moments e.g. several subsequent values missing due to a device shutdown. In this case the entire range of missing values is estimated by the same line that connects the two closest available values. Even though this technique is very simple it sometimes yields results that might be just as good as mathematically advanced techniques (S., K., C., + 19).

Figure 2: Linear Interpolation

Polynomial Interpolation

Another way of interpolating is to fit a polynomial curve to the available data points and then fill the missing values according to the resulting curve. It can be said that *linear interpolation* is a special case of fitting a polynomial line of degree 1. In this case the resulting polynomial is fit to all of the available points which causes problems in big datasets. In classical techniques such as *Lagrange* and *Newton Polynomial Interpolation* (JFE, 13) the resulting polynomial might not be of high enough degree which means it will not pass from all available points or the degree of the polynomial might be too high and cause unwanted oscillations instead of following the available data points therefore increasing the error for the missing values. This is why it is not practical to use in the case of time series and it is more practical to use techniques that focus on local points.

Figure 3: Polynomial Interpolation

Spline Interpolation

Spline interpolation is inspired by polynomial interpolation, only it fits numerous small degree polynomials from each point to the next instead of a single large degree polynomial. This way the technique avoids

fitting too complex curves while also managing to pass through all available points therefore yielding more natural looking lines. Smoother lines also mean that the technique does not alter the frequencies of the time series too much which is important in cases where periodical phenomena are analysed or sought out.

Figure 4: Spline interpolation

3 Supervised learning in healthcare

The clinical data that will be acquired in the context of the iHelp project consist of multivariate time series observations. The secondary data that will be collected through the sensor devices fall in the context of time series observations. For each patient visit (or episode), sensor data and lab test results are recorded in the patient's Holistic Health Record (HHR). Supervised learning algorithms is a sub branch of machine learning problems that relies on data where labels of the expected outcome are provided along with the feature inputs. The labels in the case of the cancer risk prediction model are the levels of the expected risk of developing that cancer i.e. low, mid and high risk level.

Supervised learning techniques refer to either classification (map input to output labels) or regression (map input to a continuous output) problems. The goal is to identify relationships/correlations or reveal the hidden structure of the input clinical and non-clinical data for the correct generation of the risk level. When carrying out supervised learning, the principal circumstances are model complexity and the bias-variance tradeoff.

Figure 5: Supervised learning workflow.

Commonly used supervised learning methods that are usually implemented for performance comparisons in risk prediction, include logistic regression (LR), random forests (RF), neural networks (NN) and naive Bayesian (NB) methods.

Artificial Neuron Networks (ANNs) are developed by creating nodes (neurons) that weight certain features and produce an output value. By layering nodes in between the input layer (features; cancer risk factors) and output layer (label; future cancer occurrence) and modifying the weights during learning -through a process called backpropagation-the resulting model forms a prediction for unseen data when one of the nodes in the output layer is positive. Deep learning produces models with multiple hidden layers that can be used to quantify the complex nonlinear relationships between inputs and outputs. Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) is one class of the deep learning models that take into account the temporality in a sequence of events, and hence is well-suited for modeling and predicting a disease onset based on longitudinal

observations of clinical events. Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) is among the most popular types of RNN architectures and they have been applied to EHR data to achieve the state-of-the-art accuracy of disease predictions.

RNNs, particularly those using LSTM hidden units, are increasingly popular models for learning from sequence data. They effectively model varying length sequences and capture long range dependencies. In the context of the iHelp project we will evaluate the ability of LSTMs to recognize patterns in multivariate time series of clinical measurements. RNNs have the concept of “memory” that helps them store the states or information of previous inputs to generate the next output of the sequence, as it is shown in Figure 6. Specifically, there are operations in the LSTM cells that allows to keep or forget information while processing the time sequence. Important concepts are the cell state and the various gates. The cell state carries information throughout the processing of the sequence in a way that information from previous time steps can affect later time steps. The gates add or remove information to/from the cell state based on what information is relevant to keep or forget, as they learned during the training phase. Gates either refer to sigmoid or tanh activation functions. A sigmoid activation maps values between 0 and 1 while the tanh activation maps values between -1 and 1. Any value multiplied by 0 returns 0 so those values will be forgotten while when multiplied by 1 means that will be kept.

Figure 6: LSTM cell architecture and operations.

The performance of the developed LSTM model needs to be verified against strong baselines, including both a linear classifier like a logistic regression model and a MultiLayer Perceptron (MLP). The baseline models will be implemented on a fixed window and using hand-engineered features. The optimization objective will be set as a combination of the loss at the final sequence step and the mean of the losses over all sequence steps. In order to address possible model overfitting, some techniques such as dropout or adjusting the number of hidden units will be applied (Z., L., K., 17).

3.1 Model evaluation workflow

The performance of prediction models can be assessed using a variety of different methods and metrics both in terms of development and the external validation of the cohorts. The iHelp pilot case studies reveal a great opportunity to act as external validation in the cohorts. The model performance needs to be evaluated in terms of discrimination, calibration, generalizability, interpretability and clinical usefulness.

The Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) metric will be measured to indicate the discrimination degree of the model, since the higher the AUC is, the better the discrimination would be. ROC curve (receiver operating characteristic curve) is a performance measurement for the classification problems at various threshold settings. ROC is a probability curve and AUC represents the degree or measure of separability. AUC reveals the models capability of distinguishing between classes (the separability). AUC ranges in value from 0 to 1. An excellent model - whose predictions are 100% right- has AUC near to 1 which means it has a good measure of separability. A poor model has an AUC near 0 which means it has the worst measure of separability.

The calibration may be evaluated in terms of its intercept and its slope. Calibration refers to the reliability of the predicted risks, i.e. whether the predicted risks correspond to observed probabilities. In medical applications this is important because treatment decisions often rely on the estimated risk of disease. The calibration intercept is related to systematic under/over-prediction (H., H., T., 15). Values greater than 0 indicate systematic under-prediction while values less than 0 indicate systematic over-prediction. The calibration slope checks whether predicted risks are appropriately scaled with respect to each other over the entire range of predicted probabilities. Values less than 1 indicate overfitting, with predicted values that have too much variability.

3.2 Risk factors analysis

The two main methods of performing risk factor analysis, as investigated by (L., H., 14), are based either on expert knowledge or a handcrafted feature set. The models based on knowledge usually fix a small number of risk factors that are already validated by experts in a field and may lose valuable information that is underestimated by experts. On the other hand, models based on handcrafted feature sets identify risk factors by calculating their statistical significance to then rank all available features according to their predictive power on a task. Such a task could be regression where models such as Linear, Poisson, Cox and Lasso regression are frequently used as the core methods, or classification where Logistic Regression Decision Trees or Random Forests. Most of these methods evaluate each feature separately and lack the ability to evaluate the relationship between features.

3.2.1 Methods based on Deep Learning

In recent years deep learning techniques have improved the state of the art in many fields such as Computer Vision (CNNs, Autoencoders), Natural Language Processing (RNNs, LSTMs) and have even been applied on healthcare datasets. However due to the large complexity of these models it is still not always clear what internal rules they have learned to achieve their performance. The concepts and knowledge they extract from input features is different according to architecture and task but understanding them usually involves visualizing the inner layer features. Authors in (S., Q., 16) describes a method that investigates the latent representation of hidden nodes and analyzes the relationships between latent features and input risk factors. By manually categorising input features into similar risk factor groups they assess each risk factor's importance by plotting the inner activation of the models by risk factor groups. By training a Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM) or an Autoencoder neural network and visualizing the neuron's activations the

authors see if the neurons that contribute to the output score are activated for features that concern similar risk factors. Such features are considered to be important risk factors. Similarly feature groups that don't contribute to the output score aren't considered risk factors by the model. We estimate that such a technique could be applied if we have target features to perform supervised learning on the relevant WP data to find the most important risk factor groups.

3.2.1.1 Restricted Boltzmann Machines

RBM is a generative stochastic graphical model that is restricted to form a fully connected bipartite graph between its visible units and hidden units. The difference compared with simple feedforward neural networks is that each edge in the graph is bidirectional. RBMs are able to learn a probability distribution of the inputs and capture higher order correlations of the input units. They are used to investigate a representation of the input features using fewer hidden units to represent the problem. RBMs can be trained in supervised or unsupervised manner depending on the task. Since RBMs are bidirectional the training process is harder than simple feedforward neural networks and they need a gradient-based algorithm called *contrastive divergence* to be efficiently trained.

3.2.1.2 Deep belief network

By stacking multiple RBMs on top of each other we can get a more powerful generative model than a single RBM called *Deep Belief Network*. Each RBM layer is connected with the next in a directed manner. It performs a linear transformation of the previous layer's features, just like a neural network, and feeds the outputs to the next level. They too can be used in an unsupervised or supervised manner which means that they can be used to do both feature learning and classification. The training process follows a greedy layer-wise procedure where each next layer is added on top of the network and only the top layer is trained as a single RBM using contrastive divergence. The basic idea of the greedy layer-wise strategy is that after training the top-level RBM of a n-level DBN, one changes the interpretation of the RBM parameters to insert them in a (n + 1)-level DBN. Note that a 1-level DBN is actually an RBM. When the layer is trained the weights are "frozen" and a new layer is added and the process repeats.

3.2.1.3 Stacked denoising autoencoders

An encoder is a deterministic mapping process which maps an input x to a hidden representation y usually using a nonlinear function. The same latent representation can be mapped back into a reconstruction z with another process, the decoder. By minimizing the difference between z and the initial input x the model will be forced to learn a good and robust set of features y that represent x well enough for z to be properly reconstructed. Recently Deep Neural Networks have been used as base models to make state of the art autoencoders. In such cases one feedforward network is used for dimensionality reduction and thus performs the encoding and another is used to generate data as close to the original as possible. Autoencoders can also be used to rectify faulty or noisy data by training them to ignore the types of expected noise (V., L., L., + 10).

3.3 Latent features analysis

The mixed representations of the inputs that the models learn by adjusting their inner parameters are the latent features. Basically the models learn to combine the input features in ways that help it deal with the task at hand. For image datasets where deep learning has recently shown great achievements, a deep neural network will learn abstract visual features in a hierarchical manner such as pixel combinations that

are then used to detect edges or corners which are then combined to find shapes and finally entire objects. However, on HER datasets the input features are tabular. This means that the model can only try to make combination out of input features and estimate which of them has a clear effect on the output. Therefore, to understand the knowledge the model has aggregated from the data, what we have to do is visualize the learned combinations that are generated during a forward pass of the model. To visually represent and evaluate the importance of the input features for a hidden node we can assign grey levels to each risk factor according to that node's gradients with regard to the inputs. To evaluate the risk factors quantitatively we can use the gradients with regard to the inputs to calculate the entropy of the categories of the top-k most important features for each neuron. A model having high entropy would mean that the inner neurons use features from different categories to map the inputs to the outputs and that there is a weak coherence amongst the features extracted in each neuron. In our case that would mean that features belonging to the same category (e.g physical activity) cannot be used by themselves to make clear estimations but have to be combined with various other factors. On the other hand, a model that has low categorical entropy indicates that there are groups of categories that have clear effect towards the value of the outputs.

4 Unsupervised learning in healthcare

Techniques for early risk identification, predictions and assessment are a central part of iHelp Platform and are closely linked with requirements to be set in T2.1 - “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” and T2.3 - “Functional and Non-Functional Specifications”.

Another dependency identified is with T3.1 - “Data Modelling and Integrated Health Records” as this task defines the common conceptual data model of iHelp - the HHRs.

During our discussions with medical partners and other consortium members, a consensus was build that processed data sets will include from one hand Incoming data from sensors – measurements of heart rate (HR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and oxygen saturation (SpO2), number of steps etc, and periodic answers to predefined questionnaires from the other.

This chapter outline and present in a high level some of the most commonly used techniques for unsupervised learning in healthcare domain for anomaly detection and early risk identification that has to be adapted for the iHelp goals i.e.:

- to identify hidden trends and patterns in existing data
- to identify personalised healthy targets for monitored parameters,
- critical or alarming limits per user per parameter to be identified

A larger set of data processing techniques applied in similar projects is currently provided as draft requirements, functional and non-functional specification, data models, parameters and even the use cases and scope of pilots listed as dependency are all currently in development.

A reduced subset of unsupervised learning techniques that are going to be actually used in iHelp, including use cases that they will address will be delivered as a part of next version of this document that is due in M22

The application of outlined solutions and their effectiveness largely depends on availability of domain specific data and how those algorithms will be trained and combined.

- There are also other factors that should be taken into account with iHelp approach of data clusterization hidden trends and patterns detection and identification of health issues, so that unsupervised learning techniques can help us with the tasks of building knowledge, research direction pre-assessment, hypothesis validation and of course for early risk identification and assessment introduction of cyclicality (periodicity) of the research should be anticipated in order to be able to make comparisons with averaged data from comparable previous periods with already known natural cyclic variations, for example: week, month, season, lunar month.
- For each of those types of periods, a specific patient profile should be calculated and used for further analysis.
- Search for deviations (anomalies) from the average values for previous periods, approaching or crossing the personalised limit values or critical limits and tracking of trends in the deviations should be based primarily on comparable profiles.
- Abrupt deviations may be due to measurement errors and a mechanism for filtering them should be anticipated before data has been used for further processing and analysis.

- Potential checks for small deviations caused due to external factors, like weather conditions or stress can improve accuracy of the algorithms.

4.1 Anomaly detection

Anomaly detection is an important area in unsupervised learning that can be applied as part of the iHelp project. It will target identification and detection of pancreatic cancer-specific anomalies within datasets of healthy and affected populations in various stages of progression. As this is a rare disease the synthetic data sets described in section 7 may be used to increase the accuracy.

At a later phase identified factors will be used for classification of patients and users in a risk profiles and identification of sudden deviations that may need instant reaction or even medical treatment.

The most promising methods applicable towards iHelp use cases and targets are:

- **Decision Trees:** A decision tree is a flowchart-like structure in which each internal node represents a "test" on an attribute (monitored physiological attribute, here), each branch represents the outcome of the test and each leaf node represents a class label (normal or abnormal).
- **Random Forests:** The random forest is an ensemble approach primarily based on decision tree which, in ensemble terms, corresponds to a weak learner. Random forests help by averaging multiple deep decision trees, trained on the same training set but on different parts, with the aim of reducing the variance so that there is no overfitting of training sets.
- **k-Nearest Neighbours:** Instance-based classifiers such as k-NN operate on the principle that unknown instances can be classified by relating the unknown to the known according to some distance/similarity function.
- **Linear and Additive Regressions.**
- **Decision Stump:** The decision stump is a machine learning technique which basically consists of a decision tree with one internal node (the root) which is immediately connected to the terminal nodes (its leaves).

Detailed information and comparison between all of them and their results in health care domain can be found in (P., S., 15).

The above algorithms can be adapted in the context of iHelp to allow discovery of cross dimensional connections and dependencies between different parameters, e.g., relationship between blood pressure and heart rate, such as simultaneous increase, decrease, average distance between measurements, etc.

Combining sensor and primary data with data collected via questionnaires will enable tracking the results changes, trends and personalise targets when applying diets, changes in physical activity, identify stress, etc.

Another possible direction could be identification of connections with external events - climatic measurements, such as temperature, atmospheric pressure, humidity; magnetic storms, etc.

4.2 Time series analysis

Following techniques for health analysis of human daily physical activity based on data taken from smart watch sensor have been anticipated.

- Principal component analysis (PCA): As a dimensionality reduction algorithm, PCA is a data pre-processing method that allows shifting of m-dimensional X data to n-dimensional Y data with minimum loss.
- Random forest algorithm: Random forest method is a classification method that is performed using a large number of tree structures instead of a single tree structure. In this method, samples from the data set are selected by Bootstrap method and classification trees are created. Using these classification trees, the observation class is decided for each tree, and the most repeated class value is selected among the classifications. The method used to create each tree in the random forest method is important in terms of determining the outcome.
- Nonstationary Distributions and Unit Roots: Unit roots can arise in multivariate time series, that is, where a vector of observations is recorded at each time point. In such cases, there may be some linear combinations of the vectors that form stationary time series and other linear combinations that are nonstationary. These results appear under the name “co-integration analysis” and “reduced rank regression”. Another possible research is “trend breaks” that can identify if one mean exists during the first period of data collection versus a second one later. This method allows determination of the break points in series and identification of cases where a seemingly nonstationary time series are in fact stationary around two or three different means

Details about application of those algorithms in healthcare domain as well as their usage and comparison of archived results are discussed in (B., S., P., 18).

Anomaly detections in time series can also be performed by using deep learning algorithms, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) as suggested in (H., W., 20).

4.3 Artificial learning techniques

The objective of unsupervised learning is to identify the inherent structure of unlabelled data. The primary goals of such unsupervised data processing are clustering, density estimation, and representation learning. Artificial intelligence methods applicable for processing of the results obtained by wearable devices are described in (N., A., K., + 22). For analysing data collected via wearable devices principal component analysis (PCA) and auto-encoders have been proposed and evaluated. Exploratory analysis and dimensionality reduction have been the other two common use cases used in unsupervised learning. In scenarios where the fully autonomous dataset analysis is impossible, unsupervised methods can be used to gain initial insights into the data and those insights can be used for testing different hypotheses.

4.4 Other techniques

Mental stress detection and analysis of physiological measurements like heart rate variability (HRV), electrodermal activity (EDA), and respiration are the main subjects in (T., P., S., + 20). The article presents multiple personalized models based on an unsupervised algorithm, the Self-Organizing Map (SOM). Clusterization methods that have been outlined and compared include Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM), Hidden Markov Model, K-Means and Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (HDBSCAN). GMM and K-Means are similar partitioning methods that base the cluster structure on the distance of the observations, but GMM does not estimate the covariance structure.

Several other approaches can contribute to the achievement of iHelp project goals:

- Data-driven Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) combined with decision-making based on distance-based detection techniques.
- Feature extraction by Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) modelling; dimensionality reduction by a deep autoencoder; and feature classification via the Mahalanobis distance metric.

A combination of Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), a MLP model, a LSTM model, and an ensemble model combining predictions of the ARIMA, MLP, and LSTM models calibrated to predict the expenditures on different medications.

5 Survival estimation

Survival estimation also known as time-to-event analysis is the estimation of the time between an exposure and an event. Relevant data is modelled either in terms of the probability that an individual survives past a certain point in time (survival functions) or in terms of the probability of having an event at a certain time (hazard functions). In the case of the project it could be the time between diagnosis and passing away or healing of the patient. There are generally non parametric models that yield results for the entire population and models that take patient characteristics into consideration when performing the estimation.

5.1 Non-Personalized

The simplest survival estimation technique is the **Kaplan Meier** estimator (G., K., K., 18). It basically estimates a single survival estimation curve for an entire population using only one feature: individual survival times. The resulting curve cannot give a personalized estimate of the survival of a patient but it can be used as a baseline technique or a tool to study different subsets of populations.

$$S(t_i) = S(t_{i-1}) \left(1 - \frac{d_i}{n_i}\right)$$

- $S(t_{i-1})$: the probability of being alive at t_{i-1}
- n_i : number of alive patients before t_i
- d_i : number of events at time t_i
- $t_0 = 0, S(0) = 1$

5.2 Personalized

As mentioned above the Kaplan-Meier technique describes the survival of a person using a univariate approach which does not allow for personal estimations. The simplest technique that addresses this issue is **Cox proportional hazards** model (G., K., K., 18). This technique aims to evaluate simultaneously the effect of survival times with other factors. It does so by calculating the baseline hazard function and multiplying it by the individual's hazard ratios as seen in the formula below.

$$h(t) = h_0(t)e^{\sum_{i=1}^n b_i x_i}$$

- $h(t)$: the hazard function with covariates x_i as inputs
- the effect of the covariates x_i is measured by the coefficients b_i
- h_0 : baseline hazard, determined by the entire population

These hazard ratios use the results of a multiple linear regression that estimates the risk level of a patient to estimate the patient's individual hazard function proportionally to their risk level. The survival function can then be estimated with regards to the person's hazard function.

Instead of using a logistic regression to amplify a basic survival function that is derived from the entire population, nonlinear functions can be used to estimate the survival functions for subpopulations. The simplest algorithm is the Survival Tree where a Decision Tree is used to split the population into different groups and a baseline hazard function is calculated for each of these subsets of the initial population. The patient's survival function is then determined by their personal risk score combined with the baseline function of the subgroup they were categorized to by the decision tree.

This allows the model to split higher and lower risks of population so that an individual's survival function is based on patients with more similar characteristics to them as well as their own characteristics. Extending that concept other classifiers may be used instead of a Decision Tree such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting or even deep neural networks like in the case of DeepSurv for even better classification.

$$h(t) = h_i(t)e^{\sum_{i=1}^n b_i x_i}$$

- $h(t)$: the hazard function with covariates x_i as inputs
- the effect of the covariates x_i is measured by the coefficients b_i
- h_i : baseline hazard for the specific class, determined by the classification algorithm

Another group of techniques focuses on utilizing unsupervised learning by performing clustering (s.a K Means or hierarchical clustering) of the patients based on risk profiles. By trying to find subgroups of population in the feature space instead of using classifiers they base the time to event predictions on groups with similar characteristics.

In the earlier Cox regression models it was assumed that patient's covariates are constant across time. However, in our project variables values will change through time (especially for secondary data). For this purpose, it is important to be able to handle time varying data. It is possible to handle such cases by modifying the CoxPH model by extending the dataset with start-stop format so as to denote the time boundaries for which the covariates had each specific set of values. Then the time varying CoxPH algorithm makes the estimation of the hazard ratios by taking into account only the relevant time periods for each feature combination and event occurrence. This way the changes that have happened to features during the trial are accounted for when estimating the changes in target features and predictions.

6 Application on synthetic data

In the previous chapters various algorithms for prediction and risk assessment have been outlined. None of them is applied to data collected in iHelp, since the studies that will provide the iHelp datasets have not yet started. In the absence of iHelp data at this phase, in this chapter we present a workflow for the learning of predictive and generative models on synthetic data. This is data provided by a simulator, and although the behavioural attributes to be collected in iHelp will be quite similar, there is no claim that the attribute values, prediction outcomes and groups of simulated people have any clinical resemblance with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) patients. In the following sections we will briefly present the simulator that provides synthetic data, followed by specific examples of learning on the synthesized data, both for predictive and for generative models.

6.1 Simulation for synthetic data

While at this stage of the iHelp project there exist primary (clinical) retrospective data, there are no secondary (Real-world/behavioural) data, especially correlated with the primary, nor of a longitudinal (across time) nature. In the absence of such data, and in anticipation of the data to be collected in the iHelp clinical studies, we have built a Real-World Data (RWD) Simulator (P., K., M., 21) that can provide synthetic data to be used when building and testing our model learning and inference pipelines.

The RWD simulator accepts demographic and behavioural information of the simulated people and simulates days of their lives. This input information forms the behavioural phenotypes. The demographic information includes gender, date of birth, height, weight, health status, employment and country of residence. The behavioural phenotypes enumerate the tendency of the people towards activities related to six behavioural traits: indoor and outdoor entertainment, indoor and outdoor athletics, inactivity, and work. For the purpose of the data synthesis for the early iHelp learning experiments we have defined the four behavioural phenotypes of Table 1. The actual behaviours are obtained by Gaussian dithering of these values with a small standard deviation.

Table 1: The four behavioural phenotypes of the early iHelp experiments in terms of the six behavioural traits of the simulator.

Behaviour	Health	Outdoor athletic	Indoor athletic	Outdoor entertainment	Indoor entertainment	Bed lover	Work-aholic
Athletic	[80, 90]	30	25	10	5	25	5
Normal	[60, 70]	20	15	15	15	20	15
Unfit	[40, 50]	5	10	20	25	15	25
Feeble	[20, 30]	5	5	10	50	10	20

Groups of activities are defined for each of the six behavioural traits. For example, outdoor athletic activities include walking, hiking, running and bicycle riding. Every time the simulated person is about to select a new activity, they refer to their assigned behavioural trait to select the next activity group. The selection is non-deterministic, but the chances of each activity group are weighted by the personality, the time of day and the recent history of activity selection. Once the activity group is selected, an activity within the group is chosen randomly. The duration of the activity is chosen based on a Gaussian duration model that each activity has, and the remaining stamina of the person.

The duration of the activity is simulated in small time steps, the simulator time delta, which defaults to five minutes. For every simulation time delta, each activity generates values for each RWD measurement by defining models of the measurement x as:

$$x = \begin{cases} 0 & u < T \\ N(m, \sigma^2 | a) & u \geq T \end{cases}$$

where u is a random variable uniformly distributed in $[0, 1]$, T is a threshold value in $[0, 1)$ that depends on the activity a , and $N(m, \sigma^2 | a)$ is a Gaussian random variable of mean m and variance σ^2 that also depend on the activity a . The mean m also depends on the available stamina of the simulated person. The threshold T is usually zero, resulting in values drawn from the Gaussian distribution. It is close to unity for activities wherein some non-zero measurements can appear sporadically, such as non-zero steps while working or sleeping, or floor climbing while walking.

Most activities diminish the stamina of the people, i.e., the available pool of energy to keep doing high-intensity activities. Some leisure activities do replenish stamina though, but it is mainly sleep that does the trick. The level of replenishment depends on the person's health and quality of sleep.

Care is taken to respect weekends and vacations based on the country of residence of each person, whereupon work is eliminated (unless there is a strong work behavioural trait). There are random events that temporarily affect the health of people (illnesses and accidents, even mood-related events). Their probability increases as health is reduced. Health is reduced constantly by age, but it is also affected by long-term behaviour; weight gain and lack of exercise or quality sleep will, in the long run, reduce health. The opposite behaviour will improve health.

The simulated RWD are complemented with reports from questionnaires. Every question is defined, together with a model that determines the answer the simulator should give. The model equations are defined using any of the data produced by the simulator (either measurements or reports), including their short- and long-term averages and trends. For example, the answer to the "ability to perform the usual activities" question is modelled with a mean value of:

$(100 - \{HEALTH_SHORT\})/20 + \{PAIN_SHORT\} + \{HEADACHE_SHORT\} - \{MOOD_SHORT\} + 2$
and a constant standard deviation of 0.5. Similarly, the answer to the mobility ability question is modelled with a mean value of

$$5 - \exp(\{STEPS\}/3000)$$

and the same constant standard deviation. In the above expressions $HEALTH_SHORT$, $PAIN_SHORT$, $HEADACHE_SHORT$ and $MOOD_SHORT$ refer to the short-term averages of the equivalent symptom, and $STEPS$ refers to the total steps walked in that day.

The RWD simulator is implemented in Python and generates RWD for every delta time interval. It also stores all simulated physical exercise sessions and all answers to questionnaires. The generated data are stored into CSV files containing the dynamic info, i.e., the RWD for all time delta intervals, the daily aggregations of all generated RWD and the answers to questionnaires, as well as the static info of the participants (the behaviours). It requires 80ms on average to simulate a person-day on a seventh generation Intel i7 CPU. The simulator has been employed to generate 114 weeks of data for 2,000 people of all behaviours shown in Table 1.

6.2 Predictive modelling

In this section we learn and analyse a predictive model, as an example of supervised learning. We first define the learning experiment in terms of input attributes and outcome to predict. We then train a Random Forest (RF) predictor. Then we discuss the important attributes in the model inferences employing SHAP analysis. The section concludes with a proposal for risk assessment, based on accumulating the decisions of patients across time.

6.2.1 Inputs and outcomes to predict

The RWD simulator has generated a large number of daily vectors each consisting of a multitude of attributes. Every day the people assess their health outlook by answering a related questionnaire. We want to predict the health outlook variation between the assessment to be made in the beginning of the week, based on the assessment of the beginning of the previous week and all data accumulated about the person in this week. The accumulated data are represented by the short-term (weekly) averages of the different attributes, as well as their trends, i.e., the normalised variation of the weekly averages from the long-term (quarterly) averages.

We selected a subset of the attributes as inputs. These are:

- The steps walked, calories burned, *sleep quality*, *body mass index*, *mood reported* and *water consumption* (short-term averages and trends – 12 attributes)
- The health outlook self-assessment of the previous week in the five-level scale used in the related question (short-term average and trend – 2 attributes)
- The *age* (static info – 1 attribute)

In total, there are 15 input attributes.

The outcome to predict is the binary-quantized version of the weekly health outlook variation: Is the person perceiving an improvement of their health, or a worsening after the week they just had?

In total there are 114 (weeks) times, 2,000 (people) weekly vectors of 15 input attributes and one outcome to work with. They are split into training (60% of the people), validation (20%) and testing (20%) sets.

6.2.2 RF predictive model

A random forest classifier is learned on the training data, using the validation data for hyperparameter tuning. The balanced accuracy of the prediction is shown in Figure 7, where the hyperparameter tuned in the number of estimators (trees) in the Random Forest. The achieved validation and testing accuracies, as well as the confusion matrix are also shown for the best RF learned.

Figure 7. Learning of the RF binary health outlook variation classifier.

Working on the train and validation sets is done in the model learning workflow. The inference workflow utilises the testing set. Since the testing accuracy is even higher than the validation, and we have not retrained our model including the validation set after hyperparameter tuning, in the rest of the inference results shown in the following sub-sections we have merged the validation and testing sets.

6.2.3 Explaining model decisions

The derivation of the attributes that are most influential towards positive or negative outcomes per person in a short time interval is important for the iHelp virtual coaching service. To do so, a second part of the inference workflow involves explaining the decisions. We employ SHAP analysis of the decisions which yield the importance of the different attributes on the decisions. The results are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: SHAP analysis of decisions.

As can be seen from Figure 8, across all four simulated behaviours, the most important attribute is the BMI trend, followed by the short-term averages of the steps walked and the calories burned. Similarly, the trend

of the water consumption is the least important attribute, followed by the short-term average of the water consumption, the age and the sleep quality trend.

6.2.4 Risk assessment

Risk assessment using model decisions is very important for iHelp. In this particular example we provide well-being assessment as the accumulation of the decisions across time. This assessment ranges from -1 (extreme risk) to +1 (zero risk – perfect well-being outlook). Please note that the well-being assessment (W) can be transformed into a risk assessment (R) by negating, shifting and scaling as follows:

$$R = \frac{1 - W}{2}$$

Figure 9 depicts the histograms of the well-being assessment for each of the four behaviours. While the feeble and unfit histograms are quite distinct from any of the normal or athletic ones, the latter two are quite overlapping, indicating that positive health assessments can be obtained not only for people of athletic disposition, but also normal people who exercise somewhat. Nonetheless, the average well-being assessments are quite distinct and the Bhattacharyya coefficients of every histogram pair are quite acceptably small.

Figure 9: Histograms of the well-being assessment conditional to the behaviour group of each person.

6.3 Generative modelling

Meaningful clusters of patients are useful to have in iHelp. The usefulness refers to the existence of common characteristics in these clusters, like common inference results or matching of these clusters to known patient behaviours. In this section we learn generative models as an example of unsupervised learning. We do so by clustering the patients into groups and modelling each of the groups.

6.3.1 Clustering

The attributes forming the input vectors to be clustered are those of the predictive modelling, appending to it the prediction outcome, resulting to vectors of 16 attributes. Hierarchical clustering is employed on the vectors. The tree is constructed using Euclidean distance and Ward linkage, while it is pruned at a maximum tolerated distance of 100, resulting to 9 clusters, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Hierarchical clustering of the people.

6.3.2 Modelling clusters

Each of the clusters has its attributes modelled using Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM). The number of Gaussians in each model is determined automatically by an iterative process where GMMs are trained using the Expectation-Maximization algorithm, and if the matching between the resulting distribution and the histogram is not satisfactory, the worst-matching Gaussian is split into two and the process is repeated.

The resulting GMM models for the 16 attributes (rows) and the nine clusters (columns) are depicted in Figure 10 (left) and Figure 10 (right).

Figure 11: Models for the first half attributes of all 9 clusters.

The obtained clusters can be validated into data-driven phenotypes of the people. The obtained clusters should include people from one of the behaviours. This is tested in Table 2, where the rows correspond to the nine clusters. The first column contains a human-readable ID for the cluster. The next 4 columns contain the number of people in the given cluster (row) coming from each of the behavioural groups (columns). The clusters are scored (6th column) based on how many people in it do not correspond to the predominant behavioural group, thus each row should have a single non-zero entry in columns 2 to 5 for a cluster score of 100. The final column shows the percentage of the population attributed to the corresponding cluster.

Figure 12: Models for the first half attributes of all 9 clusters.

Table 2: Validating clusters into data-driven phenotypes based on behavioural group matching.

PHENOTYPE	FEEBLE	UNFIT	NORMAL	ATHLETIC	SCORE	PERCENTAGE
UNFIT	2	70	11	0	84.34	20.39
FEEBLE	85	15	0	0	85.00	24.57
NORMAL-ATHLETIC	0	1	22	16	56.41	9.58
NORMAL	0	2	34	6	80.95	10.32
UNFIT (2)	1	3	0	0	75.00	0.98
NORMAL (2)	0	0	1	0	100.00	0.25
UNFIT (3)	1	24	0	0	96.00	6.14
ATHLETIC-NORMAL	0	0	12	15	55.56	6.63
ATHLETIC	0	0	13	73	84.88	21.13

The weighted score of all clusters is 65.8%, mainly because well-being assessments overlap across neighbouring behavioural phenotypes. Please note that two neighbouring non-zero entries are to be expected, especially so for the normal and athletic behavioural groups whose well-being assessments have significant overlap. Hence it should not be a surprise that two of the phenotypes are quite balanced mixtures of the normal and athletic behaviours. Clusters with high scores and significant percentages of

appearance in the population are validated into data-driven phenotypes. Note that the description of these phenotypes in terms of the included behaviours are listed in the first column.

Finally, the well-being assessments of people are revisited in Figure 13, this time from the cluster viewpoint. The histograms conditioned upon the cluster are in most cases distinct, showing how well-being assessment can be expected from the cluster of the person.

Figure 13: Histograms of the well-being assessment conditional to the cluster of each person.

7 Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI

This task also checks the applicability of the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI developed by the High-Level Expert Group on AI (issued by the EC on 8 April 2019) and provides a report in the relevant deliverable i.e. D5.1, D5.2 and D5.3.

Among others, iHelp will produce AI based techniques and algorithms, in order to enable early identification of Pancreatic Cancer. Under T5.1, these algorithms aim to reveal hidden patterns and trends in real-time/prospective data, in order to make predictions and also perform assessment of relevant identified risks. More specifically, the goal is to develop data analytic techniques to enable early risk identification, assessment and mitigation of measures, through the development of personalized models. As mentioned in previous chapters, the use of frugal AI techniques will enable the assessment of different clinical symptoms in relation with data coming from lifestyle, nutrition, physical activity, environmental and in general – as it is defined in iHelp- ‘secondary data’. Due to the indisputable correlation of the implementation of AI techniques and the work under this Task (and this WP), the examination of the applicability of the ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI, is more than valuable.

As stated in the “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI” document, written by the High – Level Expert Group on AI (AI HLEG) on April 2019, Trustworthy AI is based on three pillars (T., L., S., 21). Each one separately, should be met throughout the whole system’s life cycle. The first one refers to the lawful obedience of the system, including compliance with regulations. The legal sources include the EU primary and secondary law, the UN Human Rights treaties and the Council of Europe conventions, as well as numerous EU Member State laws. The second pillar refers to the ethical perspective, including compliance with ethical principles and values. Under that scope, the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE) proposed 9 basic principles.

Four of the ethical principles/ ethical imperatives that have derived from the proposed ones, are: a) respect for human autonomy, b) Prevention of harm, c) Fairness and c) Explicability. Among others, the ‘ethical for human autonomy’ principle includes the securing of human oversight over work processes in AI systems. More specifically, AI systems should not unjustifiably subordinate, coerce, deceive, manipulate, condition or herd humans. Regarding the ‘prevention of harm’ principle, it entails the protection of human dignity, mental and physical integrity, as well as the protection of natural environment and all living beings. Moreover, the ‘principle of fairness’ refers to both the sustainable and procedural dimension, meaning commitment to ensuring equal distribution of benefits and costs, as well as equal opportunities in terms of education, goods and services. Finally, the “principle of explicability” refers to the transparency and “explainability” of the information of who is/will be affected directly or indirectly. Finally, the third pillar is based on the robustness in terms of technical and social perspective. Under T5.1 of iHelp project all the AI algorithms that will be developed should comply with all pillars of the Ethics Guidelines. During the development, deployment and use of the AI algorithms specific ethical principles should be respected as declared in D1.3.

8 Conclusion

This report aims at identifying the baseline for the techniques to be utilized towards early risk identification for pancreatic cancer. To this end, in this document a thorough bibliographic review of the state-of-the-art AI/ML techniques and algorithms for early risk identification predictions and assessment were presented. Due to lack of data at this stage of the project we have been researching in the related literature, and in this report we have included the tools we identified as the most suitable and that are the ones we intend to use in the next phase of the project. It is clear now that the literature is not extensive when it comes to AI/ML for PC, nevertheless there are many methods that could be utilized as a baseline for early risk identification and predictions. This report is the first from a series that will follow and it is expected to serve as a guide for the techniques that we will possibly use as a baseline. Given that in the next phase of the project, relevant data will have been collected, the next version of the current report (i.e. D5.2) will report on the specific techniques and their implementations utilized for the project datasets.

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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ARIMA	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
ARMA	Autoregressive Moving Average
BMI	Body Mass Index
CA	Consortium Agreement
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma Separated Values
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EDA	Electrodermal Activity
EGE	European Group on Ethics
EU	European Union
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resource
GMM	Gaussian Mixture Models
HDBSCAN	Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
HHR	Holistic Health Records
HMM	Hidden Markov Model
HR	Heart Rate
HRV	Heart Rate Variability
SBP	Systolic Blood Pressure
DBP	Diastolic Blood Pressure
KM	K-Means
k-NN	k- Nearest Neighbours
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PC	Pancreatic cancer
RNNs	Recurrent Neural Networks
RF	Random Forest
RWD	Real-World Data
SHAP	Shapley Additive exPlanations
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SOM	Self-Organizing Map
SVM	Support Vector Machine